

FROM EVIDENCE TO DELIVERY:

Building an Accountable and
Adaptive Biodiversity 2037

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How can Victoria turn biodiversity ambition into measurable action on private land?

What would it take to make cross-sector partnership accountable rather than symbolic?

How can evidence help Biodiversity 2037 adapt before ecological decline becomes irreversible?

Introduction

Protecting Victoria's Environment – Biodiversity 2037 sets out a long-term vision in which Victorians value nature and Victoria's natural environment is healthy. However, Parts A and B of this white paper indicate that scientific ambition alone is insufficient. Part A found that the policy is relatively strong in scientific modelling and spatial prioritisation but weaker in explaining how evidence supports implementation, coordination and delivery. Part B found that cross-sector engagement can strengthen biodiversity policy implementation on private land, but only when it moves beyond consultation and becomes part of the delivery system (Nguyen, 2026a, 2026b).

This section proposes two complementary recommendations. First, Victoria should pilot a *Cross-Sector Delivery Framework* through regional biodiversity delivery partnerships in priority private-land landscapes. Second, the Department of Energy, Environment and Climate Action (DEECA) of Victoria should introduce *Adaptive Biodiversity Evidence Scorecards* to connect implementation activities with ecological outcomes, public reporting and adaptive improvement.

A program logic is used to evaluate the risk that increased engagement may generate visible activity without producing measurable ecological outcomes. Program logic maps the pathway from inputs and activities to outputs, short-term changes and longer-term outcomes, while making the assumptions underlying this pathway explicit. This tool is appropriate because the Biodiversity 2037 Monitoring, Evaluation, Reporting and Improvements Framework (MERIF) already applies a logic framework to describe how biodiversity activities and outputs are expected to lead to outcomes, identify key evaluation questions and support adaptive improvement (DEECA, 2025).

A 2×2 scenario-planning matrix is then used to explore how the recommendations may perform under different future conditions. Scenario planning does not attempt to predict one future. Instead, it develops contrasting but plausible futures to improve decision-making under uncertainty (Peterson et al., 2003). This is appropriate because biodiversity policy is vulnerable to climate pressures, shifting budgets, ecological disturbance and variable regional capacity.

Evidence-Based Recommendations

Recommendation 1: Establish a Cross-Sector Delivery Framework for Biodiversity 2037

Claim. DEECA should pilot regional biodiversity delivery partnerships in three priority private-land landscapes by mid-2027 and progressively scale the model by 2030. Each partnership should formally involve Traditional Owners, private landholders, Catchment Management Authorities (CMAs), Landcare networks, Trust for Nature, local councils, researchers, NGOs and responsible philanthropic or business partners.

Evidence. Part B found that biodiversity policy failure is often an implementation problem rather than a lack of ambition. Government-led approaches remain essential for regulation, funding and accountability, but may be insufficient where conservation depends on voluntary participation, trust and sustained stewardship. Martin et al. (2017) identify engagement as a weak link in biodiversity protection, while Clement et al. (2015) emphasise clear authority and shared responsibility. Galanis et al. (2026) found that trusted local facilitation reduced practical and bureaucratic barriers for Victorian landholders participating in wetland restoration. Mitchell et al. (2017), Graham et al. (2021) and Bush et al. (2023) similarly show that co-design, knowledge brokering and sustained researcher–practitioner collaboration improve evidence translation into practice. White et al. (2023) add that private-sector participation must be transparently scrutinised so limited positive actions do not obscure broader biodiversity impacts.

Reasoning. *Biodiversity 2037* already provides statewide direction, but implementation occurs across interconnected ecological, social and governance systems. Applying systems thinking, the proposed framework clarifies who delivers, funds, monitors and remains accountable. Partnership should complement rather than replace government authority by extending delivery capacity into landscapes where local knowledge, trusted relationships and Traditional Owner leadership are critical. This also supports intergenerational equity by embedding long-term stewardship rather than relying on fragmented, short-term activities.

Recommendation 2: Introduce Adaptive Biodiversity Evidence Scorecards

Claim. DEECA should require each regional delivery partnership to publish an annual Adaptive Biodiversity Evidence Scorecard linking implementation activities with ecological indicators and documenting how monitoring evidence informs subsequent decisions, including adjustments to regional delivery plans.

Evidence. Part B found that the literature is stronger on implementation processes than on direct ecological outcomes such as species recovery, habitat condition and landscape connectivity. This creates a risk that success will be inferred from meetings, grants or participation counts alone. DEECA already has a foundation for addressing this gap. Its *Biodiversity 2037 Monitoring, Evaluation, Reporting and Improvements Framework* (MERIF) evaluates implementation and effectiveness, while the *Biodiversity Indicator Framework* (BIF) monitors biodiversity patterns, trends, management actions and environmental changes across Victoria (DEECA, 2024, 2025).

Comparable initiatives show how scorecards can translate monitoring into adaptive management. NSW's *Ecological Health Performance Scorecards* track species, habitats, environmental conditions and fire to assess whether ecological health is improving, declining or stable, informing conservation decisions (NSW Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water, 2026). In Victoria, the Melbourne Strategic Assessment uses monitoring to assess effectiveness and adjust conservation techniques for particular species and ecosystems (Melbourne Strategic Assessment, 2024).

International guidance reinforces this approach. Dalton et al. (2024) emphasise clear objectives, suitable indicators, repeated monitoring and periodic re-evaluation. Likens (2010) similarly highlights the importance of long-term monitoring to determine whether environmental policies achieve their intended effects. White et al. (2023) support for transparent, evidence-informed biodiversity mitigation, particularly where businesses contribute funding or activities.

Reasoning. The scorecards would not replace MERIF or BIF. They would operationalise these frameworks regionally by linking activities with ecological outcomes and documenting evidence-informed adjustments. This applies adaptive management and resilience thinking: biodiversity policy must learn from changing conditions, identify underperforming interventions and adapt before ecological decline becomes irreversible.

Together, Recommendation 1 establishes the delivery architecture, while Recommendation 2 provides the feedback loop needed for accountable and resilient implementation. The SMART frameworks used to assess the feasibility and implementation of Recommendations 1 and 2 are presented in Appendices 1 and 2, respectively.

Risk Assessment

The central risk to Recommendation 1 is assuming that increased engagement will automatically improve biodiversity outcomes. A regional partnership could hold meetings, attract landholders, mobilise funding and report hectares under management while habitat condition, connectivity or species outlook remain unchanged. Perry et al. (2022) identify a similar risk in Marine Protected Areas: designation without effective management can provide “little to no real protection” while creating a false impression of success.

A program logic was applied to test this assumption. Program logic maps how inputs and activities are expected to produce outputs and longer-term outcomes, making the underlying causal assumptions explicit. This tool is appropriate because the Biodiversity 2037 MERIF already uses a logic framework to test relationships between outputs and outcomes and support adaptive improvements (DEECA, 2025). The completed program logic is presented in Appendix 3.

The analysis identifies several vulnerable links. Funding and facilitation may generate partnerships, action plans and landholder participation. However, biodiversity gains depend on ecologically appropriate interventions, substantive Traditional Owner participation, sustained landholder engagement, robust monitoring and resilience to external shocks. Ecological change may also emerge slowly, limiting short-term attribution.

This assessment strengthens both recommendations. Partnerships should not be evaluated through participation or reported hectares alone. Ecological baselines and long-term monitoring are essential. The proposed Adaptive Biodiversity Evidence Scorecards provide the feedback loop needed to identify underperforming interventions and adjust future delivery.

Exploring Possible Futures

Scenario planning tests whether the recommendations remain useful under uncertain future conditions. Rather than predicting a single future, it uses contrasting but plausible scenarios to expose assumptions and strengthen preparedness (Peterson et al., 2003). This is

appropriate for biodiversity policy because climate change can produce gradual shifts and abrupt ecological disturbances.

Two predetermined elements shape all scenarios. First, conservation beyond government-managed land will remain necessary because habitat protection, restoration and connectivity depend on mixed land tenure. Second, climate-related pressures will continue to affect ecosystems and management priorities. Thurman et al. (2022) emphasise that adaptive-capacity assessment can help natural-resource managers respond to changing climate conditions.

The scenario matrix is structured around two key uncertainties: whether government funding and policy commitment remain stable or become constrained; and whether regional delivery and adaptive-management capacity is high or low. As shown in Appendix 4, these axes generate four plausible futures:

- 1. Resilient Restoration:** Stable funding and strong regional capacity allow formal partnerships, trusted facilitation and scorecards to support sustained action, adaptation and scaling.
- 2. Well-Funded, Low-Readiness:** Resources remain available, but weak trust or unclear roles limit results. Co-design, facilitation and capability-building must be strengthened before expansion.
- 3. Adaptive Communities, Thin Budgets:** Local commitment sustains priority actions despite limited funding, but volunteer fatigue and uneven monitoring create risks. Scorecards help prioritise the highest-value interventions.
- 4. Ecological Triage:** Weak delivery capacity and constrained funding force difficult choices. Critical habitats must be protected while minimum monitoring and delivery capacity are rebuilt.

Early warning signals include declining landholder retention, delayed partnership agreements, reduced facilitator funding, weak Traditional Owner participation, inconsistent reporting and a widening gap between hectares treated and habitat-condition improvements. A major bushfire, flood or prolonged drought remains an important wild card.

Recommendation 2 is valuable across all four scenarios because it supports learning and resource prioritisation. However, scorecards cannot replace Recommendation 1: measurable ecological process still requires accountable partnerships and delivery capacity.

Major Conclusion

Parts A and B show that *Biodiversity 2037* is scientifically ambitious but requires stronger mechanisms to translate priorities into measurable private-land outcomes. Part C therefore recommends regional biodiversity delivery partnerships supported by adaptive evidence scorecards. The program logic demonstrates that funding, facilitation and stakeholder participation are necessary inputs, but they do not automatically produce ecological improvement. Progress depends on sustained landholder engagement, substantive Traditional Owner leadership, appropriate interventions, robust monitoring and the capacity to adapt when assumptions do not hold. Scenario planning further shows that these mechanisms must remain resilient under changing funding, climate and regional conditions. Victoria should make partnership an accountable pathway from engagement to ecological outcomes.

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Appendix 1. SMART Framework for Recommendation 1 - Establish Regional Biodiversity Delivery Partnerships

SMART element	Ideal scenario	Cost-effective alternative
Specific	<p>Action: Establish three regional biodiversity delivery partnerships in priority private-land landscapes.</p> <p>Lead: DEECA.</p> <p>Core partners: Traditional Owners, landholders, Catchment Management Authorities, Landcare, Trust for Nature, councils, researchers, NGOs and relevant funders.</p> <p>Goal: Convert Biodiversity 2037 priorities into coordinated, place-based on-ground action.</p>	<p>Action: Establish one or two pilot partnerships in the highest-priority private-land landscapes before wider rollout.</p> <p>Lead: DEECA with existing regional coordination structures.</p> <p>Core partners: Prioritise Traditional Owners, landholders, CMAs, Landcare and one or two key delivery organisations.</p> <p>Goal: Test the partnership model in a smaller number of landscapes before scaling up.</p>
Measurable	<p>Track active partnerships, signed partnership charters, participating landholders, Traditional Owner-led projects, hectares protected or restored, funds mobilised beyond core government funding, habitat indicators and annual reporting.</p> <p>Establish ecological and participation baselines within the first year of each pilot.</p>	<p>Track a smaller core set of indicators: number of active partners, participating landholders, hectares under protection/restoration, co-investment leveraged and one or two habitat indicators per pilot landscape.</p> <p>Establish simple baselines using existing DEECA and partner datasets in year 1.</p>
Achievable	<p>Build on existing institutions and networks rather than create a new standalone agency.</p> <p>Fund regional facilitators and dedicated monitoring capacity.</p>	<p>Use existing regional governance arrangements and staff where possible rather than appointing full new teams.</p>

	Select pilot landscapes through DEECA's existing spatial tools and consultation with Traditional Owners and local stakeholders.	Use one shared facilitator across pilots or embed facilitation in an existing agency or partner. Limit monitoring to a manageable indicator set and prioritise landscapes where baseline data already exist.
Relevant	Responds directly to the Part A implementation gap and the Part B finding that engagement is most effective when institutionalised as delivery infrastructure. Supports SDG 15, SDG 17 and SDG 13.	Still addresses the same implementation gap, but in a staged and lower-cost way. Maintains alignment with Biodiversity 2037 while reducing upfront resource demands. Supports SDG 15, SDG 17 and SDG 13 through a pilot-and-learn approach.
Time bound	Design partnerships by early 2027; establish three pilots by mid-2027; publish the first delivery report by end 2028; evaluate and progressively scale the model by 2030.	Design the framework by early 2027; establish one or two pilots by late 2027; publish a first short progress report by end 2028; evaluate feasibility and decide on scale-up by 2029–2030.

Appendix 2. SMART Framework for Recommendation 2 - Introduce Adaptive Biodiversity Evidence Scorecards

SMART element	Ideal scenario	Cost-effective alternative
Specific	<p>Action: Introduce annual Adaptive Biodiversity Evidence Scorecards for each pilot regional partnership, aligned with MERIF and BIF indicators.</p> <p>Lead: DEECA, supported by an independent scientific advisory group and regional data stewards.</p> <p>Goal: Connect partnership activity, ecological monitoring and adaptive decision-making through transparent reporting and evidence-informed adjustments.</p>	<p>Action: Introduce a streamlined annual scorecard template for pilot partnerships using existing MERIF and BIF reporting structures.</p> <p>Lead: DEECA, with technical support from internal staff and existing partner organisations.</p> <p>Goal: Improve transparency and learning without creating a major new reporting burden.</p>
Measurable	<p>Report landholders engaged, retention rates, funding mobilised, hectares protected or restored, Traditional Owner-led projects, habitat condition, connectivity measures and suitable species indicators.</p> <p>Require each scorecard to document at least one evidence-informed adjustment or explain why no adjustment was needed.</p>	<p>Report a smaller indicator set: participating landholders, hectares protected/restored, funding leveraged, one habitat condition indicator and one implementation-learning note each year.</p> <p>Require each scorecard to record at least one lesson learned and one recommended adjustment.</p>
Achievable	<p>Build on existing MERIF, BIF, Victorian Biodiversity Atlas and NatureKit systems.</p> <p>Apply a common reporting template across all pilots.</p> <p>Use a proportionate but ecologically meaningful indicator set selected for each landscape.</p>	<p>Rely primarily on existing DEECA and partner datasets and keep the template simple.</p> <p>Use a small number of indicators that are already collected or easy to collect.</p> <p>Start with pilot landscapes only and expand once reporting systems are tested.</p>

Relevant	Addresses the Part A concern about evidence transparency and the Part B weakness in direct ecological outcome measurement. Supports adaptive management, accountability and evidence-based policy improvement.	Provides a practical and affordable way to improve transparency, learning and accountability, even if full ecological monitoring is not yet possible. Still directly supports adaptive management and helps reduce the risk of symbolic implementation.
Time bound	Establish baselines by end 2027; publish the first scorecards by end 2028; conduct an independent review by end 2029; update indicators and delivery plans as required.	Develop the template during 2027; publish first pilot scorecards by end 2028; review usefulness and reporting burden in 2029; refine before broader expansion by 2030.

Problem statement/Proposal: *Biodiversity 2037 is strong in scientific modelling and spatial prioritisation but weaker in explaining how implementation, coordination and delivery will work across private land. Biodiversity action depends on landholders, Traditional Owners, Landcare groups, NGOs, councils, researchers and funders, but engagement may remain fragmented or symbolic. A delivery framework is needed to convert policy priorities into accountable, measurable and adaptive action.*

Program objective: *Establish regional biodiversity delivery partnerships that translate Biodiversity 2037 priorities into coordinated private-land action, supported by clear roles, trusted local facilitation, ecological monitoring, public reporting and adaptive improvement.*

Inputs	Activities	Outputs	Short-term outcomes	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term outcomes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DEECA leadership and pilot funding - Regional biodiversity facilitators - Traditional Owner leadership and cultural knowledge - Private-landholder participation - CMAs, Landcare, Trust for Nature expertise - Local council, NGO and university partnership - Responsible philanthropic and business funding - Existential spatial, ecological and reporting systems, incl. MERIF, BIF, the Victorian Biodiversity Atlas and NatureKit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-design partnership charters with clearly allocated roles - Identify priority private-land sites and locally appropriate actions - Engage landholders through trusted regional facilitators - Provide technical advice, stewardship support and covenant pathways - Coordinate government, philanthropic and business investment - Establish ecological and participation baselines - Collect standardised activity and ecological monitoring data - Publish annual regional scorecards - Review evidence annually and adjust delivery plans where required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Three regional delivery partnerships established - Three signed partnership charters and regional action plans - Priority restoration and habitat-protection sites identified - Participating landholders and Traditional Owner-led projects recorded - Hectares protected, restored or actively managed documented - Funds mobilised beyond core government funding reported - Ecological baselines and monitoring protocols established - Annual Regional Ecological Health and Delivery Scorecards published - Evidence-informed management adjustments documented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clearer roles, responsibilities and accountability - Improved coordination across government and non-government actors - Reduced practical and bureaucratic barriers for landholders - Stronger Traditional Owner participation in governance and delivery - Better visibility of where actions occur and how they contribute to policy targets - More consistent ecological and implementation data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustained landholder participation and stewardship - Increased uptake of restoration, habitat protection and covenant pathways - Stronger trust between regional partners - More effective mobilisation of public, philanthropic and responsible business funding - Regular use of monitoring evidence to refine interventions - Better targeting of resources towards actions demonstrating ecological value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved habitat condition and landscape connectivity - More resilient ecosystems under climate change - Measurable progress towards Biodiversity 2037 targets - Stronger accountability for private-land biodiversity delivery - Cross-sector partnerships embedded as enduring implementation infrastructure - Victoria's biodiversity is healthy, valued and actively cared for

Assumptions - Beliefs about how and why the program will work:

- Landholders will participate when practical barriers are reduced and trusted support is available.
- Traditional Owner involvement will be substantive, adequately resourced and embedded in governance rather than limited to consultation.
- Partners will share sufficiently consistent activity and ecological data.
- Restoration and habitat-protection actions will be ecologically appropriate for each landscape.
- Scorecards will inform management decisions rather than become passive reporting documents.
- Public, philanthropic and business investment will complement rather than weaken government accountability.
- Long-term monitoring will be maintained despite the time required for ecological change to become visible.

External Factors - Factors outside the program that may affect outcomes

- Climate change may alter ecosystems faster than management actions can respond.
- Bushfires, floods, droughts, pests and disease outbreaks may reduce or obscure restoration gains.
- Economic conditions and changing budgets may limit conservation funding.
- Political priorities and levels of institutional support may shift over time.
- Population growth and land-use pressures may increase competition for private land.
- Landholder willingness and capacity to participate may vary across regions.
- Data-sharing permissions, Indigenous Data Sovereignty and sensitive-species protections may affect reporting design.

Appendix 4. 2x2 Scenario-Planning Matrix

